

Greenhouse Temperature and Humidity Monitoring System using Arduino

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture is the backbone of India's economic activity and we observe strong correlation between agricultural growth and economic prosperity. If India has to emerge as an economic power in the world, we need a new and effective technology which can improve continuously the productivity, profitability, sustainability of our major farming systems. One such technology is the Greenhouse technology. Greenhouse cultivation is particularly suited to offset the effects of climate change, by definition, greenhouse cultivation is based on controlled climate parameters including temperature, humidity, light, wind and CO₂ concentration etc.

Realizing this, the present paper illustrates and discuss the Arm Cortex – M3 based smart sensor node to monitor the temperature and humidity of greenhouse. The sensor array is interfaced to monitor the physical parameters and the RF module is used to transmit the data wireless. The base station is equipped with the sink node which monitors and displays the data in user friendly format.

Keywords: Temperature, Humidity, Greenhouse, ZigBee and Arm Cortex – M3.

I. INTRODUCTION

Automatic control technology is an effective means to improve the monitoring and control systems of a greenhouse environment. Wireless sensor network (WSN) became an automation system architecture in modern greenhouses. A WSN is a group of small sensing nodes that collect the data in a given location. These nodes then send the raw data to a base station in the network, which transmits the data to a base station system that performs analysis and extracts meaningful information. This system enables to monitor various real-time data such as temperature, light levels, carbon dioxide, and humidity etc.

through the network-monitoring platform. For present research work the sensor nodes are selected and wired to monitor the greenhouse parameters temperature and humidity. The Wireless Sensor Network is widely used for several applications in various sectors due to promising features [1]. The sensor nodes are dynamic and small size so we can deploy such devices anywhere in the area under investigation. The wireless technology works with Industrial Scientific and Medical band with 2.4 GHz helps to exchange the information within the several meters in the developed network. Such devices are operates on IEEE 802.15.4 protocol [2]. The wireless technology works with on board power supply hence

interfacing of same is suitable with the selected Microcontroller. The small size and self-organization makes the wireless devices more convenient for information exchange through different topologies. Due to such silent features of wireless technology it is possible to deploy the WSN in various sectors.

The Microcontroller from Arduino family is utilized for present research work [3]. The signal is processed using the Arm Cortex – M3 based Arduino board with the help of dedicated firmware. The processed data is transmitted wireless through the WSN technology. The transmitted data is received at remote location and demonstrate the information in user friendly format. The detail system design is discussed through following points.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

Hardware:

The proposed work is to design the smart system to monitor the temperature and humidity [4] of Greenhouse. The system is wired with Arm Cortex – M3 based Arduino board. The system hardware is designed in two parts as sensor node and base station. The figure 1 (a) shows the block diagram of sensor node and figure 1 (b) shows the block diagram of base station. Image of circuit connection for the same is depicted in figure 2 [5].

Sensor Node:

The sensor node is equipped with the sensing signal conditioning, signal processing and communication capability. The sensor nodes are used to monitor the temperature and humidity of the greenhouse. The components are compared with available one and suitable is selected for present design. After selecting component and extensive study the circuit diagram is designed as shown in figure 2. The detail of the designing of sensor node

hardware part is discussed through following subsequent points.

Figure 2: Circuit diagram of sensor node

Sensors:

DHT11 Humidity Sensor: To monitor the physical quantity it is necessary to convert it in to suitable electrical quantity. It is possible due to advancement in sensors and technology. The DHT11 Humidity Sensor features a humidity sensor complex with a calibrated digital signal output [6]. Using the exclusive digital-signal-acquisition technique ensures high reliability and excellent long-term stability. This sensor includes a resistive-type humidity measurement component. The single-wire serial interface makes system integration quick and easy. Its small size, high accuracy, low power consumption and up-to-20 meter signal transmission.

Figure 3: DHT11 Humidity Sensor

DS18B20 Waterproof Temperature Sensor Cable: DS18B20 is a digital thermo probe or sensor that employs DALLAS DS18B20 [7]. Its unique one wire interface makes it easy to communicate with devices. Sensor converts temperature to a 12-bit digital word in 750ms (max). Temperature operating range from -55°C to +125°C (-67F to +257F). In addition, this thermo probe doesn't require any external power supply since it draws power from data line. The sensor is suitably implemented in any wet or harsh

environment due to its stainless steel probe head. The operating power supply range is 3 to 5.5 volt.

Figure 4: DS18B20 Waterproof Temperature Sensor Cable

Arduino Board:

The processor plays important role in embedded technology. The embedded technology is nothing but the synchronization of the hardware and software [8]. There are number of controllers are available in market, out of those Arduino Due is found suitable to implement the proposed system. Arduino Due is a Microcontroller board based on the Atmel SAM3X8E ARM Cortex-M3 CPU. It has 54 digital input/output pins (of which 12 can be used as PWM outputs), 12 analog inputs, 4 UARTs (hardware serial ports), a 84 MHz clock, an USB OTG capable connection, 2 DAC (digital to analog), 2 TWI, a power jack, an SPI header, a JTAG header. All utilized resources are configured through the Arduino IDE and discussed in software part.

XBee Module

For wireless exchange of information the suitable wireless device is necessary. On market survey it is found that there are numbers of wireless technologies are available. It is found that zigbee is more suitable than other wireless devices like Bluetooth, Wifi, IR, etc. The zigbee device has more feature than other wireless technology, so zigbee is wired for present research work.

The XBee modules operate within Industrial Scientific and Medical (ISM) 2.4 GHz frequency band [9]. ZigBee protocol which is based on IEEE 802.15.4 standard. XBee modules have source and destination addressing feature with unicast and broadcast communication support. They support point to point, point to multipoint and peer to peer communication topologies [10]. It uses DSSS (Direct Sequence Spread

Spectrum) modulation technique for communication. XBee supports Digital I/O pins, analog ADC (10-bit) input pins, PWM output etc. It has serial UART pins for communication with PC and Microcontrollers serially.

The zigbee has two operating modes namely Transparent mode (AT command) and Application Programming Interface (API) mode. It can be configured in three devices as end device, router and coordinator. To configure Zigbee the X-CTU Integrated Development Environment is utilized.

Figure 5: ZigBee module and pin out structure

Base Station:

The base station is main part of the wireless sensor network which helps to demonstrate the sensed signal by sink node [11]. The base station is equipped with coordinator node and laptop or computer. The coordinator node helps to activate the wireless sensor network and maintain the network with unique PAN ID. The computer or laptop helps to demonstrate the signal in user friendly format in text or graphical format.

Figure 6: Base Station

Software:

To synchronize the peripheral hardware wired around arduino microcontroller, the software is essential. Present system is designed to monitor temperature and humidity of greenhouse. For these sensors, signal conditioning unit and wireless

technology are wired with microcontroller. The software is co-developed with the hardware wherein the on chip ADC is configured to acquire the signal from the sensor and it is processed to convert in respective real unit. Moreover UART is configured to slandered baud rate to exchange the information.

For programming the Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) is deployed. After development of program it is uploaded in to the chip. Here no any external burner like boot loader is required to burn our code on board. Uploading on SAM3X is managed by ROM and it runs only when all data is erased and flash memory is empty. The program is loaded in the chip.

In addition to the Microcontroller programming, the

Implementation:

After development of the proposed system it is ready for implementation. The system is designed to monitor the temperature and humidity of greenhouse. To monitor these parameters system is deployed at greenhouse environment from 9 am to 5 pm and the data is stored on database. The sensor node is deployed at remote location in greenhouse and the base station is located at outside of greenhouse. The network is established deploying star topology. The deployment of sensor node is shown in the figure 7.

Figure 7: Implementation of sensor node.

III. RESULT AND CONCLUSION

As shown in figure 7 the system under investigation is implemented in the greenhouse. The temperature and humidity of the greenhouse is monitored on the base station continuously for several days. Out of the observed and recorded data from the data base of the base station, the typical data is plotted as shown in figure 8. As shown in figure, the temperature of the area under investigation is in between 20 °C to 25 °C and humidity is near about 47.2 %RH within the typical time period. On observation it is found that the system is developed successfully and implemented for dedicated application. The feature work is to send the data on cloud through IOT.

Figure 8: Plot of temperature in °C and Humidity in % RH with respect to time

IV. REFERENCES

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